

Ownership & Shareholders

Item	Details
Legal Structure	LLC (Limited Liability Company)
Number of Owners	4 shareholders (founders + early investor)
Ownership Breakdown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Michael Torres (CEO) – 42% • Sarah Chen (CTO) – 23% • David Ramirez (CFO) – 15% • Angel Investor Group (via convertible note converted) – 20%
Voting Rights	Standard LLC operating agreement – proportional to ownership
Board Composition	4-member Board (3 executives + 1 investor representative)

Capital Structure & Valuation

Item	Details
Capital Structure	Private company
Current Post-Money Valuation	\$22.5 million
Cash Position (end of last FY)	\$3.8 million

Financial Snapshot – Last Fiscal Year (2025)

Metric	Amount (USD)	Notes
Total Revenue	\$6.2 million	SaaS subscriptions
Expenses	\$5.1 million	Includes cloud hosting (\$920k), employee’s salaries and overhead.
Net Profit	\$1.1 million	First profitable year
Net Margin	18%	Solid for level of maturity

Subscription Revenue Calculation

Metric	Value	Notes / Formula
Annual Recurring Revenue (ARR)	\$6,820,000	Subscription revenue only (as per 2025)
Number of Active Clients	193	Law firms (Dec 31, 2025)
Average Annual Subscription Revenue per Client	\$35,337	$\$6,200,000 \div 187 = \$35,336.79$
Average Monthly Subscription Revenue per Client	\$2,944.73	$\$35,337 \div 12 = \$2,944.74$

Subscription Pricing Model

Tier / Product Bundle	Monthly Price per Firm	Annual Price per Firm	% of Clients (assumed)	Revenue Contribution
Starter (Pay™ only – small firms)	\$1,290	\$15,480	25% (49 clients)	\$758,520
Professional (Pay™ + Practice™)	\$2,890	\$34,680	45% (81 clients)	\$2,809,080
Enterprise (Full suite + Immigration™ + premium support)	\$4,990	\$59,880	30% (58 clients)	\$3,473,040
Total	–	–	100% (193 clients)	\$7,040,640

Additional Business Facts

- **Founded:** January 2021
- **Headquarters:** 800 Brazos Street, Austin, TX 78701
- **Target Market:** U.S. law firms (small to mid-size firms, 5–150 attorneys)
- **Customer Base:** 193 active law-firm customers (as of Dec 31, 2025)
- **Growth Rate:** 48% YoY ARR growth in 2025
- **Key Dependencies:** AWS (primary cloud provider), Stripe Inc (payments), DocuSign (eSignatures), USCIS/DOL APIs (Immigration™ product)
- **Regulatory Environment:** Heavy focus on legal-sector data protection
- **Business Risk Appetite:** Moderate – prioritizes data security and uptime over aggressive cost-cutting
- **Information Security Budget Range:** \$310,000 (5%) - \$496,000 (8%), With projected grow of 30% for 2026 the budget for the Information security could be around \$500K.